

In vitro Screening of some Aminospirans and their Derivatives against *E. histolytica*

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Amoebiasis is one of the most prevalent diseases in India and other tropical countries and is the cause of various other ailments.

A careful analysis of the antiamoebic drugs arranged¹ in nine different groups, would suggest that the drugs are structurally non-specific and none of them has been found to be universally effective or possess sustained prophylactic action. Thus, the search of antiamoebic drugs with different structural properties needs consideration. Uptil now, there is no report on the study of the antiamoebic activities of the spiro-compounds except that of Dutta *et al.*² which reported the antiamoebic activity of spiro-aminohydrochloride. We report herein the antiamoebic activity on a

number of known spiro-compounds (1a-c, 2a-d, 3a, b).

(1a-c)

(2a-d)

(3a,b)

1a ; R¹, R²=O

1b ; R¹, R²=>N-OH

1c ; R¹=NH₂, R²=H

2a ; R¹, R²=O

2b ; R¹=NH₂, R²=H

2c ; R¹=NMe₂, R²=H

2d ; R¹=NHCOCHCl₂, R²=H

3a ; R¹, R²=O

3b ; R¹=NH₂, R²=H

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Results and Discussion

The results show that all the spiro-compounds are usually more effective as amoebicide (MIC 7.8–15.6 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$) than iodochlorohydroxyquinoline (MIC 31.25) but considerably less effective than metronidazole (MIC 0.01) and tinidazole (0.02). Similar observations have been reported by us² in case of spiro-aminohydrochloride. The combined action of non-lethal doses of surfactants (31.5–60.0 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$) like Tween 80, sodium lauryl sulphate, sodium taurocholate and sodium tauroglycolate together with spiro-compounds does not show any significant change in amoebicidal activities of these compounds as tested by using the TYI-S-33 medium and NIH: 200 strain of *E. histolytica*.

Experimental

The aminospiran and their derivatives were synthesised following the reported methods³. The purity of the compounds was confirmed by m.p.s. and elemental analyses.

In-vitro screening: The technique of cultivation of *E. histolytica* was the same as reported earlier². The stock cultures of *E. histolytica* were maintained in a modification of Boeck and Drbohlav medium⁴ containing egg slant and goat serum supplemented with a loopful of rice starch. The medium was buffered at pH 7–7.4 with *M*/40 sodium hydrogen phosphate. The temperature was maintained at 37°. The cultures were examined after 72 h for viable and motile amoebae and the amoebicidal end-points (MIC values) were noted.

However, it has been argued that the variations of amoebicidal end-point are likely to occur in different xenic cultures and the end-point can only be obtained using the axenic culture of *E. histolytica*. *E. histolytica* was thus grown axenically in modified TP-S-I Diamond medium⁵. The pH of the both was adjusted to 6.8–7.0. The experimental details

of preparing xenic and axenic cultures of *E. histolytica* and the method of screening of spiro-compounds using such cultures have already been reported earlier^{2,6}.

To confirm the results, we used the recent method of axenic culture of *E. histolytica* developed and described by Diamond⁷. The amoeba (NIH: 200 obtained from Kothari Research Centre, Calcutta) were grown in medium TYI-S-33 (trypticase, yeast extract, iron, serum) containing 100 units of penicillin, 100 μg of streptomycin-sulphate and 10% bovine serum.

While finalising the minimum inhibitory concentrations (MIC) of the drugs ($\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$), the results are usually the averages of ten sets of readings. However, since we have adopted serial two-fold dilution technique in determining the MIC, standard deviations were not considered. However, the MIC values were confirmed by sub-culturing.

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